

High-z protocluster survey by Subaru/HSC

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Toshikawa et al. submitted

Hyper-Suprime-Cam (HSC)

1.77 deg² camera on Subaru

Same fields covered with WFC3 Grism in AGHAST & 3D-HST

Subaru/SCam

HSC

HSC strategic survey

- HSC SSP (Subaru strategic program): 2014-2019, 300nights
 - Wide layer: 1400deg² (i=25.9, grizy)
 - Deep layer: 27deg² (i=26.8, grizy+NB)
 - Ultra deep layer: 3.5deg² (i=27.4, grizy+NB)
 - Typical i-band seeing: 0.4-0.6 arcsec

HSC strategic survey

- So far 246deg², full color full depth

- Expected numbers:

- 10k-1M LBGs @z=2-6
- 1k-10k LAEs @z=2-6
- 10-100 LBGs/LAEs @z=7-8

The most distant protocluster at $z=6$

- 6σ overdense significance
- $\sim 6' \times 6'$ (14Mpc x 14Mpc)
- ~ 30 cluster member candidates have completely been spec. followed by DEIMOS
- 7σ overdensity in redshift space
- Further study w/CFHTLS data (Toshikawa+ 16)

HSC protocluster search

- **Systematic search of PCs at $z=3-6$ by using wide-field imaging**
- Science goals
 - Wide layer ($\sim 1400 \text{ deg}^2$)
 - **~ 1000 protoclusters** will be found at $z \sim 4$ (g-dropout)
 - diversity of protoclusters
 - Ultradeep/Deep layer ($\sim 27 \text{ deg}^2$)
 - $\sim 10-20$ protoclusters will be found at each redshift
 - redshift evolution of ~ 30 cluster members
 - various follow-up observations to reveal cluster formation and galaxy evolution. (spec., IR, radio, etc.)
- Initial results (internal data release: S16A DR ver.)
 - Toshikawa et al. 2017 --- **$z \sim 4$ PC sample over 120 deg^2**
 - Uchiyama et al. 2017 --- relation with luminous quasars
 - Onoue et al. 2017 --- relation with multiple quasars

Fixed aperture method

Apertures in which $> 50\%$ area is masked are excluded

Masked region is assumed to have mean number density

$R=1.8\text{arcmin}$ (0.75 pMpc at $z\sim 4$)
grid interval= 1arcmin

$\langle N \rangle$ and σ are measured using dropout galaxies down to 25mag

Overdensity is defined as $(N - \langle N \rangle) / \sigma$ dropout galaxies at $z\sim 4$

Maximum difference of $\langle N \rangle$ is 0.17σ among the five fields

$\Delta\text{R.A.}$ (arcmin)

Fixed aperture method

Consistency with our previous work

- COSMOS field
- Same dropout selection and overdensity estimate

Overdensity significance

- PC are defined as regions w/ $> 4\sigma$ at the peak.
- 76% of these candidates are expected to evolve into galaxy clusters w/halo mass $> 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ at $z=0$ (Chiang+13, Toshikawa, NK+ 16)

HSC Protocluster search @z~4

HSC Protocluster search @z~4

“Abundance matching” of $z \sim 4$ PCs

Observed overdensity distribution

Predicted Mass function

ACF of $z \sim 4$ PCs

- $r_0 = 35.0_{-3.3}^{+3.0} h^{-1} \text{Mpc} \rightarrow \langle M_h \rangle = 2.3_{-0.5}^{+0.5} \times 10^{13} h^{-1} M_\odot$
- Consistent with the AM estimate.
- Descendant halo mass at $z=0$: $\langle M_h \rangle = 4.1_{-0.7}^{+0.7} \times 10^{14} h^{-1} M_\odot$
- These overdense regions at high- z almost exactly marks the region of the most massive dark matter halos.

- HSC: wide-field imager to explore early universe.
- High-z protoclusters: will provide the initial conditions of clusters at their birth, and closely related to the patchy reionization. HSC survey will construct a significant number of PCs.
- Based on S16A DR, **179 $z \sim 4$ PC candidates from 121deg²**
- Dark halo mass: $\langle M_h \rangle = 2.3_{-0.5}^{+0.5} \times 10^{13} h^{-1} M_\odot$
- Next scope: SF properties of PC regions, comparison w/field
- First HSC public data release (PDR1) is now available (~100 deg² of imaging in 5 bands)
- Lots of exciting science coming soon!